

IPERION CH

SEPTEMBER 2019

Bring science to museums

Travelling with MOLAB

MOLAB

Access to advanced mobile analytical instrumentation for non invasive measurements on movable or immovable art objects

HISTORY

Growth of the MOLAB in 3 EU projects:

- Eu-Artech (2004-2009): **12** instruments, **1** provider (Italy)
- CHARISMA (2009-2014): **15** instruments, **2** providers (Italy, France)
- IPERION CH (2015-2019) - **19** instruments, **5** providers (Italy, France, Poland, Greece and Germany)

NUMBERS

5 providers in **5** countries in IPERION CH
8 calls in **4** years
68 accesses to **27** projects
more than 300 users involved across Europe

MOLAB: A MOBILE LABORATORY FOR ART

INTERVIEW TO COSTANZA MILIANI
HEAD OF MOLAB

Costanza Miliani - a senior research scientist and director of the Institute for Heritage Science-CNR in Naples, coordinator of the MOLAB platform and chair of the Access Board in IPERION CH.

What does MOLAB means? Could you shortly tell its history?

A large portion of historical patrimony cannot be moved from their usual location. Curators normally avoid moving artworks to a laboratory due to the risk to their integrity and high insurance costs. Since 2004, MOLAB (mobile laboratory) has proposed a new approach through the pioneering European projects Eu-ARTECH (2004-2009) and CHARISMA (2009-2014). MOLAB has offered a set of integrated portable instrumentations to European users for in situ measurements, more and more mobile tools and facilities flourished in different countries able to non-invasively obtain satisfying results in the study of a variety of heritage objects and relative inorganic and organic materials. The experience has been continued in IPERION CH and it will be continuing in IPERION HS (starting from 2020).

A great result of the MOLAB is its experience has significantly modified the relationships between curators, conservators and scientists.

Could you tell us more about the opportunity to access MOLAB?

I coordinate the MOLAB access to portable equipment for in situ non-invasive measurements. As development and growth of the experiences started with Eu-ARTECH (2004), MOLAB is today is composed by a coherent set of 19 single-spot and imaging techniques offered to European researchers by 5 providers (CNR-Italy, CNRS-France, FORTH-Greece, RWTH-Germany and NCU-Poland). The access to the MOLAB facility, made of instruments and skills of 5 different European providers, requires laborious management and serious experimental work including travel/transport logistics, solution of technical problems, and high skills in the execution/interpretation of the measurement. Assisted by my right-hand woman Brenda Doherty, my job implies continuous interactions with the MOLAB providers and users of our platform, in order to ensure an efficient and effective development of each access campaign.

Can you share with us what do you think is the current state of Heritage Science and what role has IPERION played in it?

In the last 20 years there has been an enormous increase of interest and number of publications on diagnostics and conservation methodologies accompanied by a more diffuse consciousness, among public and policy makers, of the heritage social and economic value. To this contributed IPERION CH and preceding projects, with the promotion of a closer cooperation among European researchers and a more diffused exploitation of small, medium and large-scale advanced facilities. Referring to MOLAB, the practice of integrated non invasive in situ investigations is today commonly accepted as an indispensable first approach to heritage studies.

Also, what do you think is the future of Heritage Science and what role has IPERION yet to play in it?

The advances of the most effective 2D and 3D imaging technologies and the development of new powerful and effective methods for data processing and management, are opening new thrilling perspectives for heritage science in the next years. The possibility offered to users to access these innovative methodologies is the right way to guarantee that Europe maintains its global leadership in the field.

MOLAB

list of
instrumentation

Multi/Hyper spectral imaging

- VIS-NIR multi spectral scanning
- VIS hyper spectral imaging
- NIR hyper spectral imaging
- X-ray fluorescence mapping

2D/3D investigations

- Optical Coherence Tomography
- Confocal microscopy
- Terahertz imaging
- Digital Holography
- NMR-depth profiling

Point chemical analysis

- X-ray fluorescence
- Mid-FTIR
- Near-FTIR
- Raman
- X-ray diffraction
- UV-vis absorption
- UV-vis fluorescence
- Time resolved fluorimetry
- NMR relaxometry
- Integrated XRD/XRF

mettere qui mappa o
strumenti

E. Munch, "The Scream", © Munch Museum, Oslo (Tech-Scream-Tech project)

"Armada Portrait of Elisabeth I", © Royal Museums Greenwich, UK (Hidden Armadas project)

Title TECH_SCREAM_TECH – TECHNical Study of CoRE Art Materials & TECHniques of SCREAM versions

User leader Irina Crina Anca Sandu

Venue Munch Museum in Oslo, Norway

Scope To investigate the six versions of the painting and collect information on the materials, the technique and the degradation processes

Title Hidden Armadas in the Armada Portrait of Elizabeth I

Users leader Clare Richardson, Birthe Christensen

Venue Royal Museums Greenwich, England

Scope To analyse the two seascapes in the background including the date they were added, pigment and materials analysis and to reveal the original colours of the painting

Title YARNWINDER. Investigating the making of the Virgin of the Yarnwinder by Leonardo da Vinci

User leader Vincent Delieuvin

Venue The National Galleries of Scotland, Edinburgh

Scope To compare the materials and techniques of the different versions of the artwork and better understand one of the recurring and most replicated motifs of the late renaissance in term of workshop production, design processes, and painting techniques

Title PEMA: Polychromy on Egyptian works of the National Archaeological Museum (Madrid, Spain). Technical study of the impact of VOCs

User leader Teresa Gómez Espinosa

Venue National Archaeological Museum, Madrid

Scope To determine and quantify the VOCs considered as problematic, as well as their possible treatment with the most effective techniques

Title Sunmix: Systematic investigation of "Sunflowers" by Vincent van Gogh

User leader Koen Janssens

Venue Van Gogh Museum, Amsterdam, NL

Scope To investigate in detail the relationship between the type(s) of chrome yellow employed and the admixture of pigments employed by Van Gogh. Additionally, to carry out cleaning tests for varnish removal and to permit a determination of the appropriate protocol/sequence of removal steps.

Title Recovering Giotto at the Basilica of Saint Anthony, Padua

User leader Gilberto Artioli

Venue Basilica di Sant'Antonio, Padova

Scope To determine the state of the architecture of the room, to test the hidden presence of existing Giotto's original frescoes and to characterize the visible parts of the paintings, in order to create a basis for the future restoration and management of this poorly known Giotto's masterpiece

V. Van Gogh, "Sunflowers", © Van Gogh Museum, Amsterdam (Sunmix project)

WHAT SCIENCE CAN HELP YOU TO SEE

new portable instruments
developed in IPERION CH

Introduction

MOLAB is developing new instruments for diagnostics on artworks. Sometimes, tools are borrowed by medical diagnostics, other times they are completely new. IPERION CH is successfully experimenting with the combination of different instruments to obtain the best results in preserving the European cultural heritage. FTIR was combined with OCT to investigate the shading process of the colours in the “Sunflowers”, painted by Van Gogh and now housed in the Van Gogh Museum in Amsterdam.

Non linear optical microscopy NLOM

CSIC, Madrid

Light can penetrate through surface, depending on its wavelength. A special optical microscope uses non-linear interaction between light and matter to scan multi-layered samples. The result are 3D images used to better understand the artistic techniques and to obtain information on the state of conservation of artworks. The tool is able to determine the chemical nature, structure and thickness of the samples without a direct contact with the artwork.

LIBS LIF RAMAN

CNRS, Paris

It is an instrument that combines three laser-based techniques. When the laser points on a sample, this emits a characteristic spectrum depending on the material. Materials can reflect, absorb, and/or transmit light rays in different ways providing simultaneously information on organic and inorganic materials that identify and characterize artworks. In latin “spectrum” means “image”, so by using LIBS LIF Raman researchers obtain images illustrating the characterisation of minerals, pigments and binding.

LIBS LIF RAMAN applied on Rubens, © Banqueting House Whitehall, (RUBENS-TCR-BHW project)

MOVIDA

<https://bit.ly/2GiMWSy>

a software for data management and analysis of non-invasive investigations

MOVIDA (MOLAB Visualization Data) is a new and innovative tool for the data management and analysis of non-invasive investigations in the Cultural Heritage field. The software was developed due to the lack of an adequate tool able to manage all the heterogeneous data generated in a in-situ multi-technique investigation of an artwork. It allows to directly manage, store analyse and perform cross-comparison of all the data obtained with the techniques usually employed in a scientific investigation of an artwork.

The java-based software not only allows for the digital preservation of all the information and knowledge, but can also be used as an analytical tool while the investigation is being developed. All the data generated in an artwork scientific investigation can be managed within the same application and the information can be easily consulted, compared and related to the corresponding areas of the artwork. The software is self-comprehensive and user-friendly and can be used by all the professionals involved in the investigation and preservation of Cultural Heritage whatever their background and computer skills are.

What users think about IPERION CH and MOLAB

The opinion of past, present and prospective MOLAB users is of great importance to us.

Our MOLAB Users are encouraged to be completely involved in each step of the access provision organization with our teams on project selection. This permits every measure to be taken to exploit the instrumental time available with the artwork and the presence of the MOLAB team experts to fulfill the aims and objectives of each individual project. Users in IPERION CH are requested to provide a feedback by means of a quick survey following access which assists the MOLAB facilities to continually improve access by assessing both the practical aspects and scientific outcomes. The organization too of yearly public user meetings permits actual users to relate their experiences of the IPERION CH access platforms to the open public. IPERION CH endeavors to build on the foundations of MOLAB to create a valuable and durable service for the future for users from multidisciplinary backgrounds.

"I HAVE FOUND THE EXPERIENCE OF WORKING WITH THE MOLAB TEAM TO BE EXTREMELY REWARDING".

"I am continually impressed by the MOLAB team's willingness to collaborate and share information, and I am immensely grateful for their input in the interpretation of results."

"All members of the MOLAB team are experts in their field, each bringing considerable knowledge and expertise with art works to every initiative."

"WITHOUT MOLAB'S EXPERTISE, IN-DEPTH ANALYTICAL EXAMINATION OF ARTWORKS IN OUR COLLECTION WOULD BE IMPOSSIBLE".

IPERION CH

in few words

What is IPERION CH?

IPERION CH is a project funded by the European Commission under GA 654028. It aims at establishing a distributed RI with a sustainable plan of activities, including offering access to a wide range of high-level scientific instruments, methodologies, data and tools for advancing knowledge and innovation in the preservation of Cultural Heritage. IPERION CH connects researchers in the Humanities and Natural Sciences and fosters a trans-disciplinary culture of exchange and cooperation for the growth of the European Research Area.

IPERION CH offers Transnational Access (TNA) to its world-class laboratories and knowledge distributed in 11 countries with the submission of single or multi-technique proposals. IPERION CH selects the best proposals and covers the costs of this activity. The TNA program offers a vast portfolio of services and activities centred on the needs of the heritage science community in Europe and Associated Countries. The combined activity promotes the development of advanced research in the examination and conservation of works of art, offering users the access to unique European resources for in situ and laboratory investigations on artwork materials through three TNA platforms: FIXLAB, ARCHLAB and MOLAB. Through the three programs of access, the project aims to deliver to the users (from experienced practitioners to primary users) not only experimental resources but also methodological approaches, compliant best practices, tools and technologies to permit them to carry out their projects in conditions otherwise impossible for them.

The access is offered to:

1. Archives in European museums or conservation institutes (**ARCHLAB**);
2. Advanced mobile analytical instrumentations for in-situ non-invasive measurements (**MOLAB**);
3. Integrated platforms where large scale facilities are coupled with medium scale installations (**FIXLAB**).

The Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure ON Culture Heritage IPERION CH launches calls for proposals twice a year. Discover how to participate in the IPERION CH website.

What's the future?

The situation of IPERION CH is evolving. The follow-up of IPERION CH is represented by the ESFRI proposal named E-RIHS (European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science). In 2017 E-RIHS started its preparatory phase (H2020-INFRADEV-2016-2, GA n.739503) that will lead to establish a pan-European research infrastructure on heritage interpretation, preservation, documentation and management.

More info : www.e-rihs.eu

Waiting for becoming an ERIC, the project IPERION HS will continue the activities of IPERION CH by offering access and training starting from April 2020. More info: www.iperionhs.eu

IPERION CH

keep in touch with us
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Produced by Laura Benassi (2019)

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